

5 Takeaways & Recommendations

1 Through a participant poll, participants from the urban planning and landscape architecture sector placed different emphasis on different **nature-based solutions (NBS) principles**:

- Environmental benefits (23%)
- Social benefits (21%)
- Co-design (19%)
- Net gain to nature (16%)
- Use natural processes (12%)
- Economic benefits (9%)

Recommendations: Promote case examples of NBS that demonstrate the use of all principles, and sustain investment for creating awareness of NBS principles.

2 All speakers noted the importance of allocating adequate resources (financial, human and time) to the **co-creation process**. The deep benefits of co-creation processes include the emergence of many **novel, unexpected ideas**, shared feelings of connection, **ownership** and **understanding of the design** and long term viability of projects. Some landscape architects and specialist nature-based enterprises are experienced in designing co-creation processes with clients and would benefit from showcasing their best practices.

Recommendations: Allocate resources for the co-creation process from the outset, communicate clearly about the objectives, listen, and be open to innovative ideas that can bring multiple benefits.

The **Connecting Nature Enterprise Platform** is a pioneering platform that supports the growth of the nature-based economy in Europe and beyond, by connecting demand with supply.

Join our community of nature-based enterprises and organisation committed to NBS in **urban planning and landscape architecture**.

Register on naturebasedenterprise.eu

3 The process of realising **nature-based solutions take time** - it may even take years. Poznan spent from 2013-2015 initiating their natural playgrounds, 2017 was spent on co-creation and implementation of the natural playground pilot's only started in 2017-2018. This was accelerated after the City of Poznan becoming a Connecting Nature partner in 2018, and now they have a network of 44 natural playgrounds in all providing a network of green spaces in a dense urban area.

Recommendations: Allocate adequate resources to a person or team to coordinate all stages of implementation of NBS projects in cities, and look for opportunities to scale out into a network of NBS projects

4 Scaling out of projects and co-creation processes have been achieved in Poznan through highly **collaborative EU funded projects**. However, cities have to search for **sustainable funding sources** to maintain NBS projects that provide multiple benefits for people and nature. At the same time, we know some corporate sectors want to invest and, in some cases, collaborate to build their green credentials. So there are questions of how to create models to connect projects and corporate finance. Financing NBS was the most requested topic for discussion at future webinars.

Recommendation: Research, develop and disseminate NBS funding models.

5 Designing new nature-based solution projects means we will need to **raise awareness** and **build understanding around the value of NBS** and why they are in our policy as adaptation and mitigation measures responding to our climate and biodiversity emergency. Cities, planners and designers have found they need to educate collaborators, clients and contractors about NBS.

In creating a network of natural play spaces, Poznan found that they were shaping the market as enterprises responded over time, and contractors rose to the challenge to deliver NBS.

Recommendation: Don't underestimate the time needed to build understanding over time. Rolling out easy pilots wins can be an excellent way to begin and raise awareness. Education should be the first step in a collaborative process.